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Towards Effective Implementation of Digital Product Passports: Stakeholders Involved and Data Requirements

Luca Carminati¹[0009-0005-1267-9190], Veronica Arioli¹[0000-0001-8013-6597], Roberto Sala¹[0000-0001-9397-1364], Fabiana Pirola¹[0000-0003-4633-7568] and Giuditta Pezzotta¹[0000-0001-7983-8356]

¹ Dipartimento di Ingegneria Gestionale dell'Informazione e della Produzione, University of Bergamo, Viale Marconi, 5 - 20044 Dalmine (BG) - Italy

Abstract. In recent years, the concept of the Digital Product Passport (DPP) has become increasingly important, particularly for enabling traceability and sustainability along the value chain. This study examines the role of the stakeholders involved in the DPP and the information to be included, based on a systematic literature review and an analysis of major European projects on the topic. The objective is to provide a clear overview of the stakeholders who could be involved and the relevant information that could be included, identifying any gaps to be addressed for an effective implementation of the DPP in the manufacturing context. The results of the analysis highlight that, despite the initiatives to regulate the DPP, significant open issues persist, such as defining the roles for the involved parties and optimizing the information to facilitate the creation of value-added services. Finally, the concept of the Digital Product Service System Passport (DPSSP) has been introduced, an extension of the DPP designed to support smart and personalized services.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Product-Service Systems (PSS), Manufacturing, Digital Product Service System Passport (DPSSP), Data sharing, Industry 5.0

1 Introduction

In the last decade, data has become increasingly strategic for business decision-making, representing a valuable resource for gaining competitive advantage [1]. However, companies often prefer to keep their data confidential, which can limit opportunities for collaboration and innovation [2]. Greater collaboration between different actors in the value chain can improve performance, foster innovation and contribute to new services development, creating value for all parties involved [2], [3].

Before the emergence of the Digital Product Passport (DPP) concept, information within companies' networks, especially in the context of product-related services like maintenance, was typically exchanged through closed systems like PLM and ERP platforms, which were often limited to internal company processes or bilateral interfaces [4]. In recent years, the DPP has been proposed as a potential tool to enhance data

management and facilitate its exchange [5]. DPP, as defined by Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of June 2024, consists of product-specific data with two purposes: (i) establishing mandatory requirements for green public procurement, and (ii) creating a regulatory framework to prevent unsold consumer product destruction. While this initiative aims to improve the Circular Economy (CE) and European environmental sustainability, facilitates resource efficiency, extends product lifespan, and supports responsible end-of-life management [6], [7], the objectives and potential of DPP extend well beyond sustainability issues [8].

According to Plociennik [8], DPP enables stakeholders - manufacturers, distributors, regulators, and end users - to share product-related data throughout the entire lifecycle, improving value chain collaboration and product traceability. DPP also drives operational efficiencies through digitalization [5] since, by improving data accessibility and standardization, it enables process optimization, accelerates certification procedures, and enhances product benchmarking [8]. However, effective DPP implementation requires complete and standardized data, achieved through solid collaboration between value chain stakeholders [8], [9].

Beyond its role in product traceability and regulatory compliance, DPP data could also be leveraged to improve service offerings [10]. In Product-Service Systems (PSSs), defined as "a marketable sets of products and services capable of jointly fulfilling a user's need" [11], data and information are essential for effectively customizing service offerings based on customer needs [3]. To maximize the value (e.g., increased customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, or revenue growth) and effectiveness of decision-making, companies must acquire information from other value chain actors, beyond their internal data [12].

To address these challenges, and considering the current lack of clarity regarding actor roles and data requirements, this paper aims to identify the key actors involved in DPPs and the essential information to be included. Specifically, the study addresses the following Research Questions (RQs):

- RQ1: Who are the key actors involved in the deployment and use of DPP?
- RQ2: What information should be included in DPPs to enable their practical use across different lifecycle stages and business models?

The article is structured as follows: Section 2 will describe the methodology used to collect DPP information through literature analysis and major European project findings. Section 3 presents the results which Section 4 discusses, focusing on DPP information requirements and stakeholder roles and involvement. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study, outlining future research directions and limitations.

2 Methodology

DPP represents an emerging field in scientific research [13]. The topic currently shows limited scientific literature and lacks a unified, comprehensive framework of its main themes [6], [13]. Due to these limitations, a State-of-the-Art (SotA) analysis has been supplemented with an Analysis of European Projects (AoEP) and their deliverables

related to DPP. This combined methodology provides a comprehensive overview of research developments and current progress in the field.

2.1 State of the Art (SotA)

The SotA analysis was conducted through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) following the PRISMA methodology guidelines to ensure research reliability and transparency of results [14]. The review began on November 19, 2024, using the Scopus database, selected for its comprehensive collection of scientific articles and established reputation. As previously mentioned, the research questions addressed: (i) the complete set of actors that could be involved in DPPs and (ii) the information that could be included in the DPP. To address these questions, the following query was structured: TITLE-ABS-KEY("Digital Product Passport" OR "Digital Product Service System Passport" OR "product passport" OR "material passport").

The query was intentionally kept simple. Adding acronyms like "DPP" or "DPSSP" would have been redundant and risked introducing noise from documents using these acronyms with different meanings (e.g., "Digital Production Planning"). Articles using these terms consistently include their full forms in the title, abstract, or keywords.

In addition to DPP, the search also considered the Digital Product Service System Passport (DPSSP) as a concept that extends DPP by incorporating PSS and service principles. This inclusion aimed to explore whether the concept has been addressed in scientific literature. However, as will be demonstrated subsequently, this concept has not yet been formally developed and addressed in scientific literature.

Finally, while the search primarily focused on understanding DPP in manufacturing, it was not limited to specific sectors to capture relevant information from all the domains that could be applicable to manufacturing. The search was also filtered to include only English-language papers from specific subject areas: Engineering, Computer Science, Energy, Environmental Science, Business Management and Accounting, Social Sciences, Decision Sciences, and Economics, Econometrics and Finance. These fields were selected to cover key DPP development aspects and avoid excluding relevant articles that answer the research questions: technical implementation (Engineering, Computer Science), sustainability and energy efficiency (Environmental Science, Energy), business applications (Business Management, Economics), and relevant decision-making processes for industry adoption (Social Sciences, Decision Sciences). Given the topic's novelty, no timespan limits were applied, and both journal and conference papers were considered. As a confirmation, it emerged that most articles were published within the past four years.

The initial query using the previously mentioned inclusion criteria yielded 221 papers. After title screening, 139 papers were excluded, leaving 82 papers for Stage 2 (abstract review). The abstract screening led to 65 papers proceeding to full-text review. The final selection included 29 papers that explicitly addressed DPPs or closely related concepts, which were then incorporated into the state-of-the-art review. Figure 1 summarizes these steps.

Fig. 1. PRISMA flow diagram.

2.2 Analysis of European Projects on DPP (AoEP)

A comprehensive mapping of developments from European projects concerning the DPP was also conducted. This phase proved to be fundamental since much of the innovative DPP research is derived from European Commission-funded projects with publicly accessible results. The analysis enabled mapping of relevant sectors, actors, and information that could be incorporated into the DPP, integrating these findings with the SotA analysis.

The AoEP began in November 2024 through the [EU CORDIS database](#), focusing on DPP-related projects. This search was performed in the database using the same keywords as the literature analysis, without applying any filters (e.g., time). Once again, DPSSP projects were not identified. Nine relevant projects, listed in Table 1, were selected for detailed analysis of their published deliverables.

Table 1. Overview of EU-Funded projects focused on DPP.

Acronym	Project ID	Program	Start-End
PESCO-UP	101138367	HORIZON	1 Jan 2024 - 31 Dec 2027
CLC-SDPP	101182727	Single Market Programme (SMP)	1 Jan 2024 - 31 Dec 2025
R-evolve	101182221	HORIZON	1 Nov 2024 - 31 Oct 2028
DigiPass	101138510	HORIZON	1 Apr 2024 - 31 Mar 2027
DaCapo	101091780	HORIZON	1 Jan 2023 - 30 Jun 2026
CIRPASS	101083432	Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)	1 Oct 2022 - 31 Mar 2024
CIRPASS-2	101158775	Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)	1 May 2024 - 30 Apr 2027
DPP-CEN	101182744	Single Market Programme (SMP)	1 Jan 2024 - 31 Dec 2025
CircThread	958448	HORIZON	1 Jun 2021 - 31 May 2025

Only five projects (DaCapo [15], CIRPASS [16], CIRPASS-2 [17], DPP-CEN [18], and CircThread [19]) published deliverables related to the researched topics specified in the previous subsection at the time of analysis, which formed the final sample of analyzed European projects.

3 Results

The analysis of the SotA and AoEP has allowed the identification of several contributions to the research questions posed at the beginning of the work.

Before directly answering the research questions, Table 2 presents an overview of the main sectors analyzed across the selected articles and projects, providing insights into research directions (discussed in Subsection 4.1).

Table 2. Overview of key sectors in selected articles and projects.

Sector	SotA Ref.	AoEP Ref.
Manufacturing	[5], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27]	[15], [19]
Electric Vehicles (EV), EV Batteries and Electronics	[28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34]	[15], [16], [17], [18]
Construction	[35]	[17]
Automotive	[36]	/
Aeronautics	/	[15]
Furniture	[37]	/
Textile	/	[16], [17]
General	[7], [8], [38], [39], [40], [41], [42], [43], [44], [45]	[19]

The first objective of the conducted research was to identify the actors potentially involved in DPP processes. Literature and scientific research have not yet universally defined the possible roles of the actors in DPP, although they recognize the need to distinguish between those who can write certain information and those who can only read it [40]. Defining these roles is essential for data traceability, reliability, and security. It establishes clear accountability for who provides, modifies, and accesses critical product information.

However, it is not helpful to define the roles of actors a priori on a general basis, because the role of the same actor might vary depending on the specific information being examined and on the objectives of the specific DPP. For this reason, Table 3 and Table 4 lists the potentially involved actors with their related references, deferring to the next section the detailed discussion on access permissions - which actors can write specific information, which can only read it, and which have no access to it. In Tables 3 and 4, the actors have been categorized according to the classification developed by King (2023) [40], whose research also identified all the detailed actors listed in the tables below.

Table 3. Actors who could be involved in DPP.

Actor	SotA Ref.	AoEP Ref.	
<i>Solution stakeholders</i>	IT developers and database experts	[38], [40]	[46], [47], [48]
	Data analyzers	[8], [23], [40]	
	Business analysts	[40]	
	Service providers	[20], [22], [40]	[46], [47]
	Independent parties (for trustworthiness)	[40]	
<i>Governance stakeholders</i>	Policy makers	[38], [40]	[46], [47], [48]
	European commission	[40]	[46], [47], [48]
	Competent national authorities	[8], [40]	[46], [47], [48]
<i>Societal stakeholders</i>	Public	[40]	
	Academic institutions	[40]	
	Consumer associations and organizations	[40]	[46], [47]
	Market surveillance authorities and external auditors	[38], [40]	[46], [47]
	Public interest organizations	[40]	
<i>Product stakeholders</i>	User stakeholders	<i>Detailed in Table 4</i>	
	End-of-life stakeholders	<i>Detailed in Table 4</i>	
	Resource stakeholders	<i>Detailed in Table 4</i>	
	Producer stakeholders	<i>Detailed in Table 4</i>	

Table 4. Details of product stakeholders that could be involved in the DPP.

Actor	SotA Ref.	AoEP Ref.	
<i>User stakeholders</i>	Importers	[40]	[46], [47]
	Dealers	[40]	
	Repairers	[8], [38], [40]	[46], [47]
	Distributors	[8], [23], [40]	
	Maintainers	[23], [40]	[46], [47]
	Retailers	[8], [24], [38], [40]	[46], [47]
	Customers	[8], [20], [22], [24], [38], [40]	[46], [47]
	Consumers	[38], [40]	
<i>End-of-life stakeholders</i>	End-users	[23], [40]	[46], [47], [48]
	Resellers	[38], [40]	[46], [47]
	Upgraders	[40]	[46], [47]
	Remanufacturers	[20], [38], [40]	[46], [47]
	Recyclers	[8], [20], [22], [23], [38], [40]	[46], [47]
<i>Resource stakeholders</i>	Final disposers	[8], [38], [40]	[46], [47]
	NGOs	[40]	
<i>Producer stakeholders</i>	Environmental organizations	[40]	
	Manufacturers	[8], [20], [22], [23], [38], [40]	[46], [47], [48]
	Suppliers	[8], [20], [22], [23], [24], [40]	
	IP holders	[40]	

The second objective of the analysis was to identify the information types and data that could be potentially included in the DPP. These vary in nature depending on the stakeholders' objectives and the intended uses. Based on the literature review and AoEP, Table 5 presents the information, categorized by the authors, that could be included in the DPP.

Table 5. Information that could be included in the DPP.

Category	Information	SotA Ref.	AoEP Ref.
<i>Identification and permissions</i>	Degree of accessibility for partners	[40]	
	Author authentication	[40]	
	Type of data carrier used	[40]	
	Roles of different partners in the passport	[40]	
	Write and read permissions	[40]	
	DPP ID		[49]
<i>Product model</i>	Product value and images	[24], [25], [43]	
	Commodity codes	[43]	
	Manuals and instructions	[8], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [36], [40], [43], [45]	[49]
	Warranties	[20], [23], [36], [37]	[49]
	Symbols and labels	[20], [37], [45]	[49]
	Certifications	[22], [25], [37], [40]	[49]
	Support documentation	[8], [20], [24], [36], [37], [40], [43], [45]	[49]
<i>Production batch</i>	Batch number	[8], [23]	
	Date	[23]	
	Destination	[23]	
	Quality inspection reports	[23]	
	Operators involved	[23]	
	Production data and mix of products	[23]	
<i>Specific item linked to the DPP</i>	Past and current owners	[23], [28], [40]	
	ID	[20], [21], [22], [25], [28], [33], [37], [40], [45]	[49]
	Bill of materials	[8], [20], [21], [23], [24], [28], [32], [33], [37], [40], [43], [45]	[49]
	2D drawings and CAD models	[25], [42], [43]	[49]
	Technical properties	[20], [21], [23]	[49]
	Assembly and disassembly information	[20], [25], [28], [33], [37], [40], [42]	[49]
	Storage requirements	[25], [40]	
	Installed software	[25]	
	Manufacturing information	[8], [20], [21], [24], [25], [28], [32], [33], [40], [42], [43]	[49]
	Shipment and logistics details	[20], [25], [33], [36], [37], [40]	
	Quality checks	[36]	

	Operational and performance data	[21], [22], [24], [25], [33], [36], [37], [40], [42], [43]	[49]
	Product and component conditions	[21], [24], [25], [28], [33], [37], [43]	[48], [49]
	Maintenance log	[8], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [28], [32], [36], [40], [42], [43], [45]	[49]
	LCA data	[24], [37], [40], [42]	
	Remanufacturing and refurbishment data	[32], [33], [36]	
	Waste management data	[32], [37], [40]	
	Recycling methods	[8]	
<i>Indicators</i>	Circular economy metrics	[8], [25], [28], [43], [45]	[49]
	Environmental, social and economic indicators	[21], [22], [37], [40], [43]	[49]
	Calculation methodologies	[25], [28]	
<i>Value chain actors included in the DPP</i>	Email addresses		[49]
	Registered trade names	[43]	
	IDs	[37], [45]	[49]
	Addresses		[49]

4 Discussion

4.1 Sectors under research and key actors involved in DPP

The SLR identified many DPP studies across various sectors, as detailed in Table 2. The research primarily focuses on the manufacturing and electric vehicles/batteries sectors (respectively 31% and 24% of studies from the SotA out of the total), which have the highest number of publications exploring the DPP topic and its applications in remanufacturing, traceability, product lifecycle management, and sustainability. Only a few studies have explored DPP applications in construction (4%), automotive (4%), and furniture sectors (4%). Many studies take a broader perspective, proposing general guidelines for DPP implementation across different sectors (33%). Regarding European projects, out of the five identified, electronics and batteries lead with four projects, followed by manufacturing and textiles with two. Construction and aeronautics are each referenced in one project. However, significant work remains to establish a robust and common framework for DPP structure and implementation. This is particularly urgent for sectors that will be the first to adopt DPP under the new EcoDesign regulations, according to Regulation (EU) 2024/1781. These sectors include iron and steel, aluminum, textiles, furniture, tires, detergents, paints, lubricants, chemicals, energy-related products, and information and communication technology products and electronics [50], [51]. However, some sectors present in the regulation remain underexplored in scientific research. This is likely because the focus has been on areas with more complex products (such as manufacturing and electronics) or where end-of-life

management is more immediate (e.g., the textile sector), as these offer a broader ground for discussion and DPP application proposals. Nevertheless, it is essential that frameworks developed for the DPP also consider these sectors to create modular models adaptable to different contexts.

A crucial aspect for better understanding the DPP concept was clarifying the stakeholders involved and their roles, as detailed in Table 3. The SLR revealed several key actors: solution stakeholders (including IT developers, data analysts, and service providers), academic institutions and consumer organizations, governance stakeholders (such as policymakers and national authorities), and product stakeholders. Product stakeholders, among the most frequently cited actors in DPP literature, include user stakeholders (importers, repairers, retailers, maintainers, consumers) who share information along the value chain. End-of-life stakeholders interact with user stakeholders, resource stakeholders (such as NGOs that monitor regulatory compliance for sustainability), and producer stakeholders. Manufacturers, suppliers, and IP holders emerge as primary stakeholders, likely contributing the most to DPP development and implementation. However, the literature does not clearly identify the roles of different actors in the DPP - a point that needs better clarification in future works, especially concerning the reluctance to share valuable data among actors [52].

The AoEP revealed that European projects identify similar actors to those found in scientific literature. Among them, governance stakeholders receive particular attention, which could be a characteristic of European projects that typically emphasize institutional roles more than academic literature does. However, also European projects lack clear identification of actors' roles regarding specific information to be included in the DPP. They only establish that actors can have two roles in the DPP: reading and writing information.

4.2 Information that could be included in DPPs

The analysis performed in this study contributes to the identification of data to be included in the DPP (Table 5). Given the large amount of information that could be included in the DPP, the inclusion of specific information requires careful evaluation. It is necessary to identify relevant stakeholders and determine high-quality and appropriate data inclusion based on the company's business objectives [53]. This approach will prevent data redundancy and ensure collection of only business-critical information. Indeed, maintaining the DPP, including its updates, represents a cost in terms of time and resources (both economic and otherwise). Therefore, it is crucial that the information included, and consequently the process for its insertion, maintenance, and updating, adds value to the company [54].

Furthermore, a distinction between essential information (e.g., necessary to enable a service or process) and optional but useful information could optimise the strategic and sustainable adoption of a DPP. Given the previous discussion on data relevance, this distinction takes on particular importance. However, current scientific literature provides limited guidance in this direction, especially regarding what information is necessary to enable specific services or PSS business models. While some articles discuss service-relevant data, such as maintenance logs and repair history, these mentions are

scattered and lack systematic organisation. There is also no comprehensive framework showing how the DPP could effectively support service enhancement and delivery across the product lifecycle, particularly for end-of-life stages (e.g., refurbishment, recovery, remanufacturing, revamping, etc.). This gap indicates the need for clear requirements for integrating the PSS concept into the DPP tool and explains why there are no publications in Scopus regarding the DPSSP concept. Therefore, it is essential to clarify which information should be included in the DPP to enable customer services, thus defining both PSS integration into DPP and DPP exploitation for smart PSS purposes. Including information that enables new services in the DPP would ensure better cooperation between actors, promoting the development of new product-service solutions while improving the efficiency of existing services.

Additionally, there is a critical need to further explore stakeholder roles in reading/writing information and to provide more detail on includable information (such as static/dynamic nature, EU regulatory requirements, and relevance in lifecycle phases) to clarify for industrial actors how the DPP could be used and what could be achieved through its exploitation for all product lifecycle phases: beginning of life, middle of life, and end of life.

Connected to this aspect, the literature implicitly [20], [24], [35] and explicitly [23] highlights the need to explore relationships between product and its components in the DPP context, but a clear definition of interface and structure is needed to add business value. To minimize data redundancy and optimize information distribution for specific components (such as the Remaining Useful Life of critical parts), a hierarchy of DPPs should be established where sub-levels of critical components enrich the product DPP. This will enable specific services, such as revamping, predictive maintenance, and informed sales of used (but not end-of-life) components. As illustrated in Figure 2, each component could be associated with its own DPP, which records not only its specifications but also service-related information. This structure supports the creation of a DPSSP, integrating service history and enabling advanced functionalities, including component tracking, reuse strategies, and predictive maintenance. In this regard, it is also important to define guidelines to help companies understand when and why component DPPs can usefully supplement and detail the product DPP, evaluating factors such as management costs, information specificity, and component criticality.

Figure 2. Component-Level DPP and PSS Integration.

4.3 Key Gaps Between SotA and AoEP

As discussed in the previous subsections, the analysis of literature and European projects has revealed several critical gaps in current DPP research. Table 6 summarizes these gaps alongside observations from both the state of the art and European project reviews.

The research gaps provide an opportunity to develop the DPSSP concept. This integrated framework would enable companies to leverage DPP data beyond regulatory compliance while driving innovative and service-oriented solutions that meet customer needs and sustainability goals. The DPSSP framework must address several key challenges: lack of standardized methodologies, unclear stakeholder roles, undefined data-sharing responsibilities and missing criteria for data inclusion.

The DPSSP framework should be developed as a common foundation for sector-specific solutions while supporting modular adaptations for unique industry and product needs. This approach promotes interoperability, reduces duplication, and aligns efforts across sectors. The research direction between generalization and specialization is gradually emerging in current literature, without a clear and defined direction yet. Therefore, the debate between these two themes remains a crucial area for future research, specifically regarding which elements of the framework could be generalized and which should remain sector specific. In this context, the DPSSP should support structured, multi-level DPPs that better reflect product-component relationships, making data more available across all lifecycle stages and for proposing component-based services.

Table 6. Key gaps in DPP research.

Aspect	<i>State of the Art (SotA)</i>	<i>European Projects</i>	<i>Identified Gap</i>
<i>Industrial sectors covered</i>	Focus on manufacturing, electronics and batteries	Focus on manufacturing, electronics, batteries and textile	Misalignment between research focus and urgent regulatory needs
<i>Stakeholder roles</i>	Various actors mentioned but roles are unclear	Institutional roles emphasized, but still lack role clarity	Need for clear operational role definition and data-sharing responsibilities
<i>DPP structure and methodology</i>	General guidelines only, no common framework	No standardized structure in projects	Urgent need for a shared, robust implementation framework, applicable to multiple sectors
<i>DPP content</i>	Limited focus on service-related data	Unclear inclusion criteria, risk of redundancy and high maintenance cost	Need to define critical, high-quality data that is aligned with business objectives and the lifecycle stages at which it will be useful
<i>Component-level structure</i>	Suggestion to explore component relationships	No practical structure in place	Need to establish DPP hierarchies (e.g., for

			predictive maintenance, component reuse, etc.)
<i>Integration with Services and PSSs</i>	Poorly explored in literature	Not addressed in practice	Opportunity to develop DPSSP to enable smart, service-based value generation

5 Conclusion

In this study, a literature review and an analysis of completed and ongoing European projects' review on DPP were conducted, with the aim of identifying (i) the complete set of actors that could be involved in DPPs and their roles, and (ii) the information that could be included in the DPP. The work identified the actors potentially involved in the DPP, clarifying the stakeholders interested in the topic. An initial list of information, data, and indices that could be included in the DPP was also developed. These elements, although general, provide the reader with a starting point for more specific reflections on data already available to the company and those that could potentially be acquired to add value to the DPP logic. To complete the analysis, several gaps in literature on the DPP topic were highlighted, proposing the DPSSP as a concept that combines PSS with DPP, promoting better integration of services in the context of the digital product passport.

This study has some limitations. First, the observations are based exclusively on scientific literature, European projects, and the authors' personal knowledge of DPP-related initiatives. The delay in the publication of scientific articles, due to peer review processes, and in the dissemination of European project deliverables must be considered. Some of the latter might not yet be accessible to the public, especially when referring to business cases (frequent in this type of projects) where the practical application of concepts might be more advanced than what is currently published. It would also be interesting to evaluate companies' position on this topic, particularly regarding critical information to be included in specific scenarios, and on the need to develop a hierarchy of product DPPs and component DPPs to enable new services (i.e., second life).

Future developments could explore these critical issues in depth, analyzing them in detail to propose concrete solutions. In particular, the DPSSP topic and the hierarchization of product and component DPP should be explored, evaluating the benefits these could bring to the organization in proposing new or more efficient services.

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